

THE OPTIMAL DOSE OF GOA FORMOL VACCINE AGAINST RABIES PASTEURELLOSIS

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Nabieva Naima Akhmedovna

Independent researcher at the Veterinary Research Institute

Annotation: *In order to determine the optimal dose of GOA formol vaccine against rabies pasteurellosis, 30 rabbits were tested in the laboratory by subcutaneous vaccination in different doses. The study found that a single rabies vaccine against pasteurellosis had an average immune response of 1: 1,200 at 3 months and 1: 800 at two vaccines. The results of the study showed that even if 1 ml is injected subcutaneously, the effect of 3 months of immunity is found to be high, the article details.*

Keywords: *patella, bacteria, rabbit, vaccine, optimal dose, agglutination reaction (AR), immunity, antibody titer.*

Relevance of the topic: Rabbit pasteurellosis (hemorrhagic septicemia) is a very serious and dangerous disease. The disease kills many animals as a result of severe injuries to the lungs, heart, vascular system, intestines and other organs, such as sepsis, hemorrhagic inflammation, hemorrhage. Pasteurellosis develops widely in spring and summer. Additional factors, such as climate change and various toxic chemicals, are contributing factors. (Annikov VV, Krasnikov AV, Korotova DM Collection of reports in the sources cited on pages 176-177).

The incidence of pasteurellosis in rabbit farms is 70-75% and the mortality rate is 80-85%. A lot of money is spent on the treatment and control of sick rabbits. Infected rabbits lag behind in growth and development and become carriers of the pathogen. (Yatusevich A.I, Prudnikov V.S, Karassev N.F, Nekolayenko M.F, monograph 10-12 pages).

Therefore, the vaccine against rabies pasteurellosis is a very effective factor for prophylactic purposes. Taking into account these problems, for the first time in Uzbekistan, the optimal dose of GOA formol vaccine against rabbit pasteurellosis, developed by scientists of the VITI Laboratory of Microbiology, was studied in rabbits in the laboratory.

The purpose of the study. Determining the optimal dose of rabies vaccine against pasteurellosis.

In order to carry out research in this area, 30 rabbits were divided into 2 main groups in order to determine the optimal dose of GOA formol vaccine prepared from pasteurilla strains isolated from sick rabbits available in the laboratory. Group I rabbits were once vaccinated. Group II was vaccinated twice with an experimental GOA formol vaccine against pasteurellosis at 7-day intervals. Each group was divided into several subgroups and vaccinated subcutaneously with different doses of the vaccine, as shown in Table №1, in accordance with the rules of asepsis and antiseptics.

Table №1. Vaccinate rabbits with different doses of the vaccine.

/N	Number of rabbits (head)	Dose (ml)	S/N	Number of rabbits (head)	Dose (ml)	
					one time	twice
	Vaccination once		Vaccination twice			
	5	0,5	4	5	0,5	0,5
	5	1	5	5	1	1
	5	2	6	5	2	2

The general condition of all vaccinated rabbits was clinically monitored for 5 days. Blood samples were taken 15, 30, and 90 days after vaccination, and the titer of specific antibodies against pasteurellae was determined using an agglutination test (AR) to study the strength of the immune system.

Material methods and results of the study: The general condition of all vaccinated rabbits was clinically monitored for 5 days. No complications were observed during follow-up. Thirty days after vaccination, blood samples were taken from them, and the titer of specific antibodies against pasteurellae was determined by agglutination reaction (AR) and the strength of immunity was studied (Table №2). The optimal dose of the vaccine is 1: 200 in the first group, 1: 400 in the second group, 1: 400 in the third group, 1: 200 in the fourth group, 1: 400 in the fifth group, 1: 200 in the sixth group, 30 in the 15-day specific antibody titer index. daily 1: 400 in the first group, 1: 800 in the second group, 1: 800 in the third group, 1: 400 in the fourth group, 1: 600 in the fifth group, 1: 400 in the sixth group. At 90 days, 1: 600 in the first group, 1: 1200 in the second group, 1: 1200 in the third group, 1: 800 in the fourth group, 1: 800 in the fifth group, and 1: 800 in the sixth group.

Table №2. Titer dynamics (AR) of antibodies against pasteurellosis in the serum of vaccinated rabbits.

Main groups	Small groups	Vaccination schedule		Number of vaccinated rabbits	Antibody titers		
		One time	Twice		15	30	90
I	1	0,5ml	-	5	1:200	1:400	1:600
	2	1 ml	-	5	1:400	1:800	1:1200
	3	2 ml	-	5	1:400	1:1800	1:1200
II	4	0,5 ml	0,5 ml	5	1:200	1:400	1:1200
	5	1 ml	1 ml	5	1:400	1:600	1:800
	6	2 ml	2 ml	5	1:200	1:400	1:800

The study found that a 3-month-old immune response to a single rabbit vaccine against pasteurellosis averaged 1: 1,200 at a double dose of 1: 1,200. Studies have shown that a single subcutaneous injection of 1 ml has a high immune response for 3 months.

conclusion:

1. The 3-month immune response to a single dose of the experimental formol vaccine against rabies pasteurellosis averaged 1: 1200.
2. When rabbits were vaccinated twice with this vaccine, the rate was 1: 800.
3. The results of the study showed that a single subcutaneous injection of 1 ml showed a high level of 3-month immune efficacy.

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